

IMPROVING READING COMPREHENSION THROUGH NEWSPAPER ARTICLES

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Abstract

This article gives information about the benefits of using newspaper articles as material to develop reading comprehension. The article focuses on the role of real-life texts in activating the learners' thinking, expanding vocabulary, and developing critical thinking.

Keywords: Reading Comprehension, newspaper articles, critical thinking, active reading, vocabulary, text analysis

Introduction

Reading comprehension is the ability to effectively extract information from a text and process it consciously. This skill is important not only in the educational process, but also in everyday life. Newspaper articles are excellent material for developing reading comprehension. They include real-life events, a variety of topics, and different writing styles, which allows students to know a wide range of knowledge.

Main body

Newspaper articles cover topics such as events happening in everyday life, economics, and culture. This allows students to more easily get new information based on their own experiences during the reading process. Newspaper articles are written in a variety of genres: news, analytical articles, interviews, commentaries, etc. This allows students to understand different writing styles and develop reading skills accordingly and learn new vocabularies. And it often include visual elements

such as pictures, diagrams, and infographics, which help readers better understand the text and remember the information.

By reading newspaper articles, a learners not only increases their vocabulary, but also learn to look at events from different perspectives. Each article has a unique topic and introduces the reader to new knowledge, facts and statistics. This, in turn, leads to the expansion of the reader's general worldview. For example, through an article written about any news, the reader not only becomes aware of the development of events, but also seeks to understand the causes and consequences of these events. In this process, reading becomes not just a passive reception of information, but also a form of active analysis and reasoning. Thus, reading comprehension is not only based on grammatical knowledge, but also includes logical thinking, event analysis and the ability to extract the necessary information from the text.

In addition, newspaper articles are rich and colorful in terms of language. Journalists often use simple, yet effective and concise expressions. This increases the reader's sensitivity to language and helps him understand texts of different styles.. It is known that the richness of the vocabulary is directly related to the level of reading comprehension. Whoever knows more words, the learner understands the text more deeply and more easily understands the idea that the author wants to convey. Therefore, another useful aspect of reading through newspaper articles is the opportunity to learn new words and apply them in practice.

Another unique advantage of newspaper articles is their modernity and relevance of topics. In newspapers published every day, news is constantly updated, which attracts the attention of the reader and encourages them to read. For example, by reading topics ranging from local news to international relations, learners better understand the world around them. Also, various topics, such as sports, health, economics, culture, literature, science, analysis and opinion sections,

allow learner to learn variety of vocabularies. This increases the learner motivation to read, and through continuous reading, comprehension skills improve.

Of course, there are also problems in this process. For example, unfamiliar words, complex sentences, and unclear topics can make it difficult for the learner to understand. In such situations, methods such as using a dictionary, reading the article in parts, focusing on identifying the main idea, and taking notes can help. In addition, by engaging in regular reading practice, that is, reading at least one article every day, the students will constantly develop their level of understanding. Also, by discussing articles, analyzing them with friends, or expressing his thoughts in writing, the information read is understood more deeply.

Conclusion

In conclusion, developing reading comprehension through newspaper articles is an effective process that requires self-improvement, critical thinking, and regular practice. This method provides the student with not only language skills, but also the skills of thinking, logical analysis, filtering relevant information, and conscious thinking. Therefore, with the development of modern technologies, it is in the hands of each of us to improve our reading comprehension skills using online publications, mobile applications, and online newspapers. Because this skill is one of the most important supports that we will need throughout our lives.

Resources

1. "Improving Reading Comprehension" – Janette K. Klingner, Sharon Vaughn, Alison Boardman
2. Reading Strategies That Work: Teaching Your Students to Become Better Readers", Laura Robb, Scholastic, 2000
3. "Improving Reading Comprehension" Janette K. Klingner, Sharon Vaughn, Alison Boardman

